

**STUDY ON CONSUMERS' DECISION MAKING IN MOTOR INSURANCE
POLICIES:**

A BEHAVIORAL ECONOMICS PERSPECTIVE

A Report

Submitted in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for Award

of

POST DOCTORAL FELLOW

By

Dr. SUMI ALEX

Registration No: 21SUPDR004

Under the Supervision of

Dr. P S AITHAL

Professor, Department of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University, Karnataka

DEPARTMENT OF MANAGEMENT AND COMMERCE

MUKKA, KARNATAKA, INDIA

JULY 2022

Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this Report is original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This Report is my own work and does not contain any outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

Signature. :

Name : Dr. SUMI ALEX

Registration No : 21SUPDR004

Place : MUKKA

Date : 20/07/2022

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Srinivas Nagar– 574 146, Mangalore, Phone :0824-2477456
(Private University Established by Karnataka Govt. ACT No.42 of 2013.

Web:www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in, Email:info@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

Certificate

This is to certify that the study entitled “Study on Consumers’ decision making in Motor insurance policies: a behavioral economics perspective submitted by Dr. SUMI ALEX to SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY for the award of the Post-Doctoral Fellow is a Bonafide record of the research work carried out by her under my supervision and guidance. The content of the Report, in full or parts have not been submitted to any other institute or university for the award of any degree or diploma.

Dr. P S Aithal, Professor
Department of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Karnataka

Place : Mukka

Date: ____/____/____

Acknowledgements

I wish to express my profound sense of gratitude to my supervising teacher, **Dr. P S Aithal**, Department of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Srinivas Nagar, Mangalore without whose skillful guidance expert advice, this report would not have appeared in the present form. I am deeply indebted to him for the earnest interest he had shown in me and in my academic effort.

I acknowledge my sincere thanks to **Dr. Praveen B M**, Research Director, Srinivas University, Srinivas Nagar, Mangalore for holding me to a high research standard and enforcing for good research result.

I am indebted to **Rev. Fr. Baby Thomas**, Manager, St. Gregorios College, Kottarakara for giving me the consent to do Post-Doctoral research.

I also extended my thanks to **Mrs. Jiji Peter**, Principal, , St. Gregorios College, Kottarakara for providing the facility of undertaking my work smoothly. I extend my sincere thanks to **Dr. Deeja S**, Assistant Professor, St. Gregorios College, Kottarakara and **Dr Soumya Syamchand** who directed me towards Srinivas University for a PDF. I am indebted to **Dr. Seema S Nair, Dr. Remya R, Sreeja Bhaskaran and Rejitha** for their wholehearted support and inspiration throughout my work. I also thank my colleagues at the Department of Commerce.

I gratefully remember my parents, sister, brother, my husband **Dr. Shiju Mathew** and daughters **Sera S Mathew** and **Serin S Mathew**, who were a source of inspiration throughout this endeavour.

I know well that in this brief acknowledgement, I could not include all persons who provide me with data and congenial atmosphere to work with concentration. I express my heartfelt thanks to all those whom I could not mention in these pages.

CONTENTS

	Page
Acknowledgements	
List of Tables	v-vi
Synopsis	viii-xii
Chapters	
1. Introduction	1-7
2. Review of Earlier Studies	8-12
3. Data Analysis and Interpretation	13-43
4. Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Suggestions	44-47
Bibliography	48-
Publications from the Report	43-57

LIST OF TABLES

Table No:	Title of the Table	Page
1.	Tests of Normality	
2.	Reliability statistics	
3.	Non additivity perception and satisfaction of policyholders towards motor insurance policy	
4.	Demographic Profile	
5.	Satisfaction level of different motor insurance policyholders	
6.	Independent sample t test	
7.	Satisfaction level of different educational groups towards motor insurance policies	
8.	Relationship between Consumer Buying Behaviour and Satisfaction in Motor Insurance Policyholders	
9.	The Influences of Buying Behaviour on Consumer Satisfaction with Durbin Watson Test	
10.	The Influences of Buying Behaviour on Consumer Satisfaction using ANOVA	
11.	The Influences of Buying Behaviour on Consumer Satisfaction ³	
12.	Factors influencing motor insurance	
13.	Communalities of motor insurance policy holders considering the factors for joining motor insurance claim in Kerala	
14.	Total variance explained for motor insurance policy holders considering the factors of choosing the motor insurance policy	
15.	Rotated component matrix of motor insurance policy holders considering the perception	
16.	Four factors influencing motor insurance	
17.	Difference between educational qualification of respondents towards factors affecting motor insurance holders	
18.	Sources of Awareness	

19.	Challenges faced by the motor vehicle insurance holders	
20.	Challenges faced by motor insurance holders based on their gender	
21.	Challenges faced by motor insurance holders based on their education qualification.	
22.	Reason for choosing motor insurance policy	
23.	Reasons for choosing motor insurance policy based on gender	

Synopsis

STUDY ON CONSUMERS' DECISION MAKING IN MOTOR INSURANCE POLICIES:

A BEHAVIORAL ECONOMICS PERSPECTIVE

Introduction

The insurance industry in India has been growing dynamically, with total insurance premiums increasing rapidly, as compared to global counterparts. Currently, the insurance penetration in India is **3.7 percent** of the gross domestic product (GDP) as against the world average which is 6.31 percent. The life insurance sector in India is growing at 11 percent to 12 percent. General insurance is growing at 18 percent per annum, which is low in comparison with global levels. These low penetration and density rates reveal the uninsured nature of large sections of population in India, and the presence of an insurance gap. The sector has transitioned from being an exclusive State monopoly to a competitive market, but public-sector insurers hold a greater share of the insurance market even though they are fewer in number. The recent notification of 100% foreign direct investment (FDI) for insurance intermediaries (announced in the Union Budget of 2019-20) has liberalized the sector much. In this study an attempt is being made to analyze motor insurance sector which is one of the most prominent among the General insurance sector. Hence the customer perception and attitude is changing in our country towards insurance business. The motor insurance marketing has become a very innovative field in terms of providing creative services. So in this research an attempt is being made to study the customer's decision making on various car insurance policies and procedures and analyze the usage pattern of car insurance attribute attracting policy holders, opinion towards car insurance marketing efforts, which leads to creating awareness on various motor insurance policies to the policy holders of the companies. Meanwhile the problems and prospectus faced by the motor insurance policyholders will be covered in detail.

Significance of the study

Significance of the study is very relevant in all its aspects, as motor insurance is an unavoidable element in life of a common man. Understanding this research therefore:

- Provides an indepth understanding of factors affecting performance of motor insurance.
- Benefits other researchers, policy makers, development agencies (actors), and entrepreneurs who would like to venture into the insurance industry.
- Helps business practitioners, Government, Donors, NGO's, insurers, reinsurers, insured and intermediaries to understand and have advanced knowledge and information on the constraints that they are likely to face and what they have to do in order to grow through the use of insurance services.
- Supports Insurance Companies to tackle the influential factors and improve the performance of motor insurance specifically.

Research Problem

The focus of the research is to look at the consumer's decision in the selection of motor insurance policies. The overall purpose of this research is to add to the body of literature on perceptions of customers in the selection of motor insurance policies. This research will potentially provide new insights into the effect of unusually high increase in motor insurance premium and its impact.

The research was undertaken to answer the following testable questions:

1. What are the factors influencing the customers in the selection of motor insurance policies?
2. How much is the potential savings for consumers in the selection of motor insurance policies?
3. How far the policy holders have awareness towards motor vehicle Insurance policies?

Objectives of the study

- To analyze the satisfaction level of different motor insurance policyholders.
- To Assess the Relationship between Consumer Buying Behaviour and Satisfaction in Motor Insurance Policyholders.
- To analyze factors affecting Motor insurance policyholders.
- To analyze the challenges faced by the motor vehicle insurance holders.
- To analyze the reason for choosing motor insurance policy.

Research Methodology

Qualitative, Quantitative methods and a combination of both was considered while carrying out the Research.

Qualitative research methods such as interviews and observations are suitable for understanding opinions and the underlying feelings or beliefs that influence behavior.

Quantitative methods such as surveys or experiments are based on collecting numerical data and suited for examining the relationship between variables.

Review of literature

- Thaslim Arif, Dr. ksirajuddin (2011)-In this article talked about the policy holders perceptions towards the Motor Vehicle Insurance with Special Reference to POLLACHI TALUK. This study was conducted on studying the demographic profile or the policy holder's perceptions towards insurance company. The research was completed based on the interview agenda with a taster of 100 respective who are considered for the research study. The results were examined using simple measurement study, Chi-Square test and Freidman's grading test. Results discloses that male Respondents are highly ideal. The study has also initiate that the belief in the Insurance Company was the first view factors of the policy holder4s to select the insurance firm.
- Dr. Sangeetha Natarajan(2009)-in this article talked about the determinants for estimating Life Insurance corporation of India, the insurance business has suffered an extreme alteration later liberalization, globalization and privatization of the Indian budget in over-all and the insurance area particularly. For nearly four eras LIC has remained solitary performer with effective dominance in the life insurance area. The entries of so many subdivisions was likely to effects the presentation of Life Insurance Organization .The impact of not ever challenge rivalry previous, currently has to enter with the private companies who claim of the ironic and long familiarity of their associates from the advanced nations of the world and becomes domineering at this occasion to evaluate the act of life insurance Organization of India. And for estimating the routine of LIC in development.
- Dr. P G Khot Tryambak Hiwarkar(2008)-Analysis of the collision and allegation of E-commerce on the insurance and banking. In this article paper axis exclusively on the

suggestion of the internet for insurance market and banking, due to quick enlargement of information and communications technology, and most highly, the development and expansion of internet. Electronics impacts on business.

- Seema Sharma, Dr. Sujit Sikidar (2008) - A study on Performance depth of public segment insurance units after Detariffication- a study attempts to examine the growth and performance of the public sectors insurance companies operating in India in the competitive scenario. Non-life insurance sectors were driven by various tariffs prescribed by the tariff advisory committee.
- Sharma Aparajita (2011) -From this study extracted that the aims is to advance the managerial capability framework for the middle glassy managers of the general insurance sectors in India. Secondary enquiry offers the summary of existing generic capability models. The needs was witnessed for a capability based structure in the insurance area in India. Investigation was accompanied among eight middle glassy managers of the public and private area general insurance organizations. The consequences exposed the fourteen managerial: systematic skills, Communication skills, creativeness, and policymaking, ability to formulate, invention, interpersonal talent, etc. remained the utmost vital skills. Other significant skills remained communication talents, inter-personal expertise and club management.
- Varma, P R Swathy (Jan 2012) - The study effort to examine the relative performance of public and private area general insurance companies in India. Indian insurance business move into advanced Growth rate owing to recent reform. With the existence of foreign direct investments, sectors permitted up to 26% of equity, private insurer expanded the market through innovative products, creating efficiency and competitiveness in the country was the main objective behind the reform process. On one side, the issue was to capture a vast untapped population under suitable insurance coverage while the other key concern to elevate the performance of insurance co, so that they contribute more to the country's economy.
- Chun,Yan (2015)- The identification Algorithm and Model Structure Of Automobile Insurance Scam Based On Facts Mining , This paper examined the titled that the data taking out machinery to anti automobile insurance fraud. The better-quality outlier exposure technique based on the nearby neighbour with clipping rules was applied

practically to automobile insurance fraud, and the enhanced auto insurance fraud documents model and the method of Algorithm model has been confirmed by investigational analysis. Finally it resulted the Algorithm model benefits of low time complication, High appreciation rate, High exactness and low effect on the key significance of the algorithm.

References

- Dr. Natarajan Sangeetha(2013), Determinants for Evaluating Life Corporation Of India, journal Business Management and Social Science Research, Vol.2,No.9,pp-47-53, ISSN NO; 2319-5614
- U. Arif Thaslim, Dr. K. Sirajuddin,(2012) A study on policy towards motor vehicle insurance with special reference to Pollachi Taluk, International journals of business management, Vol.2, Issue 2, pp.115-119,ISSN NO: 2454 – 6119
- Dr, P G Hiwarkar Tryambak Khot ,(2008), Analysis Of the Collision and Allegation of E-Commerce On the Insurance Banking, Journals of Business Management and Social Science Research (JBM&SSR),Vol.2, Issue.6, ISSN NO:2319-5614
- Dr.Sujit Sikidar, Seema Sharma, (2008), Performance Measurement Of Public Insurance Units After De-Tarrification, Journal of Business Management and Social science Research (JBM & SSR), Vol.3, Issue.3, pp.44-50, ISSN No; 2319-5614
- Swathy P R Varma1, N Ajith Kumar,(2014), A Comparative Study of Public and private sectors in general insurance, Shodhganga: A reservoir in Indian theses @INFLINET, Vol.4, Issue 12,pp.45-73
- Sharma Aparajita (2016), Development of managerial competency framework for middle level managers of the general insurance sectors, Journals of business management and social science research (JBM &SSR), Vol.6, Issue 3, ISSN;2231-5985
- Chun Yan, Yaqi Li(2011), The Identification Algorithm and Model Construction Of Automobile Insurance Fraud based on Data Mining, Vol.6, Issue 4, PP.24-27.

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

The services industry is one of the largest and fastest growing sectors in the global market. Among the fast growing developing countries, India is distinctive for the role of the service sector. Its contribution to the Indian economy is particularly significant, with regard to employment potential and impact on national income. As per the figures available for 2021 fiscal, almost 52 per cent of India's GDP comes from the agricultural sector and the service sector is the second largest contributor with 34 per cent, out of which Banking, Financing, Insurance, Real Estate and Business Services makes 10 per cent of the GDP. Insurance is a huge and one of the most rapidly growing sectors in India with a steady growth rate of 32 to 34 per cent. The insurance industry not only generates long-term funds for infrastructure development, but also increases a country's risk taking capacity. The services industry provides massive business prospects to investors. Without the service sector's capacity to generate revenue, it would be difficult for the Indian economy to acquire the healthy place it currently enjoys on the global platform.

The insurance industry as a financial service is considered as one of the important segments in an economy for its growth and development. Insurance companies sell, or underwrite policies and receive premiums in return. They pay out a portion of these premiums when claims are made, and invest some of it in stocks, bonds and other investment products. The industry also plays a role in the economy through claim payouts to policyholders, and through taxes paid to different levels of government on insurance premiums.

The Indian general insurance sector has started showing signs of significant changes after the opening of the industry to private players. In India, the insurance is broadly classified into two - life insurance and general insurance. Life insurance covers all risks related to the lives of human

beings and general insurance covers the rest. General insurance has three major classifications viz., Fire, Marine and Miscellaneous (motor and health are included in miscellaneous).

1.1 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

With the opening of insurance market to the private players, the market is filled up with new players which has led to the introduction of several innovative insurance products, add-on, and services. The competition among the companies has led to aggressive marketing and distribution techniques. Healthy competition is good for the companies and also for the customers. In general insurance, health and motor are the highest contributor and the fastest growing insurance sectors. It is clear that unlike from other types of insurances, the motor and health insurance are having the highest number of policyholders. The motor insurance in India is being made mandatory too. Hence in this highly competitive market where the companies are hardly struggling to capture the customers, the need and importance of measuring or rating the customer satisfaction is very high. The customer is core of every kind of business, this principle is applicable in the insurance industry too. Because of the information exposure today's customers are more knowledgeable and his expectations are very high. In order to satisfy the growing expectation of the customers, insurance companies have to render customer needed service in customer satisfying manner. In the absence of a quantitative parameter to measure customer satisfaction, it has not been possible till recently to objectively compare the level of customer satisfaction in the insurance companies and between these companies. The present study is an attempt in this direction and hence is more significant. The study of customer satisfaction will provide an insight into the weak areas of customer service and the companies can make corrective actions as and when needed. Moreover, the study will be much useful to the insurance companies, both public and private sector in framing their future marketing strategies.

1.2 RESEARCH PROBLEM

The focus of the research is to look at the consumer's decision in the selection of motor insurance policies. The overall purpose of this research is to add to the body of literature on perceptions of

customers in the selection of motor insurance policies. This research will potentially provide new insights into the effect of unusually high increase in motor insurance premium and its impact.

The research was undertaken to answer the following testable questions:

1. What are the factors influencing the customers in the selection of motor insurance policies?
2. How much is the potential savings for consumers in the selection of motor insurance policies?
3. How far the policy holders have awareness towards motor vehicle Insurance policies?

1.3 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Insurance plays an important role in the growth of an economy. India is the fifth largest country in Asia in terms of insurance premium followed by Japan, Korea, China and Taiwan. The country is geographically large and has the world's second largest population but it also has one of the lowest penetration rates for property and casualty insurance in Asia in terms of premium as a percentage of GDP. The current size of the non-life industry is Rs. 58,344 crore growing at the rate of 23.16 per cent. India is the second largest populated country in the world sheltering over one billion people. The population statistics itself is a key indicator of the growth potential of insurance industry in India.

The huge market largely remains untapped in both rural and urban India as majority of the population is still not touched by insurance companies. And this part of the population is also subject to weak social security and pension systems with hardly any old age income security. General Insurance Industry in India is booming but not to the level compared with the developed economies such as Japan, Singapore and other developed economies of the world. Thus it is an indicator that growth potential for the insurance sector is immense. Realizing this great truth, the public as well as the private players in the general insurance sector are introducing diversified and innovative products, smart marketing and aggressive distribution to extract the essence of the potential market.

As a result of Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization (LPG) of the Indian economy, just like any other business sector, insurance sector also underwent a versatile change. Monopolistic competition of public sector insurance companies came to an end, giving wider

opportunities to the customers to select their insurers as per their requirements. In today's hyper competitive environment, insurers are operating under shrinking premiums, growing customer expectations and tightening regulations which are narrowing their margins. With the entry of private players, the competition is becoming intense. Innovative products, smart marketing and aggressive distribution have enabled private general insurers to capture considerable percentage of market share and established their strong presence in the market. With a population of over one billion, national and international life insurance companies see India as a land of opportunities and a market for big business.

Now customer is the king who decides the future of the companies. The customer always demands for a product which simplifies his life by providing him tailor-made products and quality services, thus helping him to take informed investment decisions. So customer satisfaction is an important perspective that has to be taken into consideration more seriously by General Insurance Companies. In a service industry like insurance, the quality of the customer service acquires crucial significance in the context of sustained business growth. However no serious study has been conducted to evaluate the level of customer satisfaction in motor insurance sector. So the present study is conducted to evaluate the customer satisfaction.

1.4 OBJECTIVES

The broad objective of the study is to analyse the customer satisfaction in motor insurance companies in Kerala. The Specific Objectives are;

1. To analyze the satisfaction level of different motor insurance policyholders.
2. To Assess the Relationship between Consumer Buying Behavior and Satisfaction in Motor Insurance Policyholders.
3. To analyze factors affecting Motor insurance policyholders.
4. To analyze the challenges faced by the motor vehicle insurance holders.
5. To analyze the reason for choosing motor insurance policy.

1.5 METHODOLOGY

Qualitative and Quantitative methods or combination of both were considered while carrying out the Research.

Qualitative research methods such as interviews and observations are suitable for understanding opinions and the underlying feelings or beliefs that influence behavior.

Quantitative methods such as surveys or experiments are based on collecting numerical data and suited for examining the relationship between variables.

1.6 TOOLS OF ANALYSIS

The data collected was subjected to appropriate statistical and mathematical analysis, using SPSS. Statistical tools like mean, standard deviation, correlation coefficient, ANOVA, and the test of significance like t-test, Chi-square test and KMO Bartlett test are suitably employed for the analysis of the data

1.7 VARIABLES USED FOR THE STUDY

The present study attempts to assess the customer satisfaction in Motor Insurance Companies in Kerala

Dependent Variable: Independent Variable

1.8 LIMITATION OF STUDY

This study has the following limitations:-

1. As the study is primarily based on primary data, its inherent limitations are expected to affect the study. The customers were reluctant to provide details about their policies, income level etc.

1.9 PRESENTATION OF THE STUDY

The first chapter deals with the introduction about the topic, statement of the problem, objectives, hypothesis, methodology- sample design, tools for analysis, period of study, significance of the study, limitations, and Chapterisation.

The second chapter examines the available literature in connection with relationship between customer satisfaction and service quality and insurance and bank related studies.

The third chapter is an evaluation of customer buying behavior in motor insurance companies in Kerala.

The fourth chapter gives the summary of findings, suggestions and conclusion, based on the study,

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF EARLIER STUDIES

Rosander A.C. (1985) focuses specifically on the service quality aspect of insurance business, there are 3 parties via, the seller of insurance product, insurance company and the buyer of insurance product. In insurance service quality relates to six broad aspects of business quality of raw or original data, the quality of derived data quality of performance of employees at all levels, quality of service related to financial aspect's involved.

Keeling (1993) has examined the various insurance options available- commercial, property insurance, public liability policies- as well as latest developments in latent defect insurance and how this can be arranged in a proper way.

Armstrong, Ed and Buse, P. (1996) in there article projects that banks should add their percentage of after tax to 5-10 percent if "they aggressively pursue their insurance opportunity." They considers banks as the best media for insurance business. Banks can easily convert their customers to insurance policyholders without any extra effort. The author develops a Performa statement for banks selling 12 different insurance items.

Gidhagen, Mikael (1998) has made an attempt to develop a conceptual framework from a relationship perspective for the study of insurance service marketing. Deregulation and internationalization have created a new, increasingly competitive business climate. The focus of this research work is on the relationship between insurance companies and their corporate customers.

Ajay K Rajan & Mukesh Dhunna (2002) analyzed the social implications in the opening up of insurance sector to private players to find reasons as to why there was private entry after nationalization, what the social issues are so far and how the reforms in Indian insurance industry can be implemented. The reason for private players, based on competition is to enhance resource utilization, reduction in premium cost, funds to mobilize domestically, better pay packages and to attract the inflow of foreign capital. The study also reveals that most of the private players concentrate on business only in urban areas.

Gorski, Lorraine (2002a) in his article describes how insurers can use the banks' customer base to reach new customers. It is easy for the banks to act as a distributing channel for insurance products among the middle level or mass market because of the trustworthiness that they have with the banks. Banks could represent 3-4 different insurers therefore the insurance products need to be competitive (for the customer and the representative) and specific for bank employee selling. Furthermore, stable relationships are necessary and the product needs to be branded and well-advertised. Underwriting will stay with the insurers but selling may go both ways by insurance agents or bank employees.

Gorski, Lorraine (2002b) identified that Insurers have founded banks to offer their insurance products along with their routine business lines. Insurance banks have an uphill battle to convince their customers to establish a bank account because it is hard to determine when and why an insurance customer needs a bank account. On the other hand, it is easier for a bank that provides a loan to sense when insurance is necessary. Since most people already have a bank account, the customers as well as agents have to be motivated to deal with another financial institution or to switch. In addition these new institutions often have no brick and mortar establishment but rather rely on internet applications and internet interactions.

Atmanand (2003) has studied insurance and disaster management in the Indian context and made many valuable suggestions to fill the gap in the role of insurance sector in the disaster management. From his point of view insurance has got a lot to do with regard to disaster management and only very few studies have been conducted in this subject.

Aloke Tewary (2003) in his article states that skills and experience are necessary to tap the employment opportunities arising from the liberalization of insurance sector. He brings out the

difference between pure risk and speculative risk, where pure risk can be overcome only through the techniques of risk management. Insurance business needs a lot of capital, skill and talent to manage the marketing treasury operations, administration and vigilance. He discusses on the eligibility criteria for banks to enter the insurance business, the capital adequacy ratio of the bank should not be less than 10% and NDA levels of the bank should be reasonable etc.

Keerthi Pa Vijayalakshmi. R., (2009) noticed that all the respondents/ policy holders have certain level of expectations from the services that are to be delivered by an insurance company. Their expectation level varies irrespective of the demographic profile, but they look forward to excellent delivery of services. Established banks enable insurers to get into the trust business and offer a sophisticated retirement package and to be able to cross-sell insurance products to their customers and to earn free income. Increasing brand awareness, direct mailing and providing up-to-date interest rates should help to lure customers. Most insurance firms have hired experienced bankers to create and manage these banks.

Gagandeep Kaur (2011) in his Ph.D work “Employee perception and customer satisfaction: a study of selected Indian universal banks “states that positive Word-of-mouth recommendation is the most focused and most targeted marketing form. He identified reliability and social responsibility as the most important factor influencing customer satisfaction in the banking sector, because customers are attracted towards banks that are having better corporate social responsibility. He also added that the customer needs more user friendly products and services rather than readymade ones.

The foregoing review reveals that even though many studies are being conducted about service quality, customer satisfaction, tools used in customer satisfaction and problems and prospects of insurance sector, no systematic attempt is made to study on consumers’ decision making in motor insurance policies in this regard, the present study would be a pioneering venture and future researchers will be benefited.

References

1. Agus, Arawati, TQM as a focus for Improving overall service performance and customer satisfaction, Total Quality Management & Business Excellence, July/ August 2004, Vol. 15, issue 5/6, pp. 615-628.
2. Alope Tewary “Insurance - The latest Buzzword in the Indian Economy” Banking Finance Jan 2003 pp. 10-12.
3. Armstrong, Ed and Buse, P. (1996). “You’ve got the green light, what’s it worth?” *ABA Banking Journal*, Vol. 88, Sept., 13-18.
4. Atmanand (2003), “Insurance and Disaster Management in the Indian context “, Disaster prevention and management, 12(4), General review, [<http://www.Emeraldinsight.com>
5. Gagandeep Kaur, 2011. Employee perception and customer satisfaction; a study of selected Indian universal banks, Ph.D. Thesis, submitted to Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar.
6. Gidhagen, Mikael “Insurance marketing- Services and relationships” Uppsala University Press, Sweden, 1998.
7. Gorski, Lorraine (2002a). “The New Producers.” *Best’s Review*, May 2002, p.45-48.
8. Gorski, Lorraine (2002b). “Banking on Policy Holders”. *Best’s Review*, July 2002, p.44
9. Keeling .R (1993), “Latest developments in Latent Defects Insurance,” *Property Management*, 11(3)[<http://www.Emeraldinsight.com>]
10. Keerthi Pa., R.Vijayalakshmi, “A comparative study on the perception level of the services offered by LIC and ICICI Prudential “; *Indian Journal of Marketing*, pg-40-54, August, 2009.
11. Rosander A.C. (1985), “Application of quality control in service industry”, ASQC quality press

CHAPTER III

Data Analysis and Interpretation

While selecting a particular product of a particular company many factors like reputation, marketing ability of agents, advertisement, claim experiences, etc. strongly influence the customers' selection procedure. Today insurance is an inevitable element in one's life, in case of motor insurance, it is mandatory and no one can get rid of it. Despite being a small state with just 3 per cent of India's total population, Kerala accounts for 12 per cent of the road accidents in the country. The accident rate in India is 7.2 per cent for every 1,000 vehicles, but in Kerala, it is 15 per cent for every 1,000. An acquisition of motor insurance policy is mandatory in our nation for any vehicle owner and it helps the policy holders to minimize the risk of losing money in case of any theft or damage to the vehicle. The policy holders can claim the insured money only in case of any accidents or damages to the vehicle. Unlike life insurance and health insurance which need to be taken only at the will of the policy holder, motor insurance policy is mandatory as per the law in India. Hence it is essential to understand whether the customers or policy holders are satisfied or not satisfied with the policies and packages offered by the companies.

The present need of the insurance industry is not adding more and more products in to their product line; instead it should be in a position to provide tailor made products for their customers. And if the company wants to deliver such products it should first understand who are its customers and what are their needs. For the healthy growth of the insurance industry, companies should mould their services with a deep knowledge about the intrinsic mechanism. The most important aspects related to hiring of insurance are customer satisfaction and service quality. This chapter presents a detailed analysis the research was undertaken to answer the following testable questions:

1. What are the factors influencing the customers in the selection of motor insurance policies?

2. How much is the potential savings for consumers in the selection of motor insurance policies?
3. How far the policy holders have awareness towards motor vehicle Insurance policies?

Objectives of the study

- To analyze the satisfaction level of different motor insurance policyholders.
- To Assess the Relationship between Consumer Buying Behavior and Satisfaction in Motor Insurance Policyholders.
- To analyze factors affecting Motor insurance policyholders.
- To analyze the challenges faced by the motor vehicle insurance holders.
- To analyze the reason for choosing motor insurance policy.

Table 1
Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
V1	.680	305	.372*	.995	305	.359
73						

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

As per Kolmogorov-Smirnov, the test value is 0.680 and the significant value (P value) is 0.372, statistically not significant. Similarly the Shapiro-Wilk test value is 0.995 and P value is 0.359, statistically not significant. Both shown the given data is normally distributed.

Table 2

Reliability statistics

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.827	.831	85

Source: primary data

In the beginning section, the reliability of the study was checked, for which Cronbach's Alpha was calculated. According to 85 items, the Cronbach Alpha coefficient is 82.7 per cent and the Cronbach Alpha based on the standardized item is 83.1 per cent. This showed that the tool designed for administrating the data from the respondent group is comparatively reliable. The benchmark score is 70 per cent and the obtained Cronbach Alpha is 82.7 per cent found highly satisfied.

This implies that all the statement included in the interview schedule are highly reliable and inevitable. Therefore, it is treated that all score is highly relevant for the present study.

Table 3

Non additivity perception and satisfaction of policyholders towards motor insurance policy

ANOVA with Tukey's Test for Non additivity						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between People		3218.477	210	12.686		
Between Items		17706.764	70	119.788	128.89	.000
Within People	Non additivity	219.760 ^a	10	209.760	226.77	.000
	Residual				8	
	Balance	42509.836	47256	.925		
	Total	41119.596	47257	.929		
Total		52726.361	47414	1.323		
Total		55544.837	47715	1.395		
Grand Mean = 3.6529						

Source: primary data

Tukey's estimate of power to which observations must be raised to achieve additivity = 2.364.

ANOVA with Turkey's test not additivity is also done for the present research. According to the table the P value is 0.000 which is lower than 5 per cent showed that the data is stable and stabilized; therefore, there is no additivity is reported.

Table 4
Demographic Profile

Profile	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	150	51.7
	Female	140	48.2
	Total	305	100.0
Region	Southern Region	113	37.0
	Central Region	97	31.8
	Northern Region	95	31.1
	Total	305	100.0
Marital Status	Married	275	90.2
	Unmarried	30	9.8
	Total	305	100.0
Educational	Up to Plus Two	6	2.0

qualification	Graduation	128	42.0
	Post Graduation	6	2.0
	Professional	165	54.1
	Total	305	100.0
Occupation	Business	18	5.9
	Professional	36	11.8
	Employee	205	67.2
	Agriculture and Allied	46	15.1
	Total	305	100.0

Source: primary data

Objective1: To analyze the satisfaction level of different motor insurance policyholders

H₀ : There is no significant difference between satisfaction level of male and female towards motor insurance policies.

Table 5

Satisfaction level of different motor insurance policyholders

Dependent Variables	Gender	N	mean	SD
Quality Product (QP)	Male	150	3.3077	1.1926
	female	140	3.1481	1.3258
Psychological Safety(PS)	Male	150	3.9923	1.2595

	female	140	4.7037	1.8456
Insurable	Male	150	3.7500	1.2546
Risk(IR)	female	140	3.5190	1.2584
Agents Motivation(AM)	Male	150	3.2540	1.3654
	female	140	3.2690	1.2548
Financial Securities(FS)	Male	150	3.4560	1.3695
	female	140	3.2140	1.2546
Coverage Meets Expectation(CME)	Male	150	3.1450	1.3654
	female	140	3.2580	1.2548
Individual Attention(IA)	Male	150	3.6540	1.3695
	female	140	3.8540	1.2546
Flexibility(F)	Male	150	3.8590	1.2548
	female	140	3.4820	1.3654
Reasonably	Male	150	3.8540	1.2549
Priced(RP)	female	140	3.4570	1.6549
Customer Relationship Management(CRM)	Male	150	3.0580	1.8546
	female	140	3.4980	1.3654

Source: primary data

Psychological Safety(PS) was found to be the most prominent attribute among female respondents ($\bar{X} = 4.7037$). ‘customer relationship management is the least least prominent among female customers ($\bar{X}= 3.0580$), The following hypothesis was tested.

Table 6**Independent sample t test**

Test variables	Leven's test for equality of variance		T test for equality of means		
	F	Sig	t	df	Sig
Quality Product (QP)	0.031	.785	1.025	289	.248
Psychological Safety(PS)	2.308	.158	0.095	289	.897
Insurable Risk(IR)	5.162	.025	4.046	289	.000
Agents Motivation(AM)	7.425	.008	1.275	289	.204
Financial Securities(FS)	5.984	.014	0.310	289	.657
Coverage Meets Expectation(CME)	5.258	.018	0.772	289	.444
Individual Attention(IA)	0.185	.068	2.180	289	.031
Flexibility(F)	4.358	.038	0.770	289	.442
Reasonably Priced(RP)	0.784	.378	2.333	289	.022
Customer Relationship Management(CRM)	0.925	.348	0.139	289	.884

Source: primary data

A greater than 0.05 significance of F statistics fails to reject Levene's null hypothesis that variances are equal. In all such cases the t statistics of independent samples t test, when variances are unequal becomes irrelevant. The null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the satisfaction of motor insurance holders across categories of gender fails to get rejected, at 5 per cent level of significance in the cases of insurable risk (.000, 4.046), individual attention (.031, 2.180) and reasonably priced (.022, 2.333). No statistically significant difference could be traced across categories of gender, in all the other cases.

H₀ : There is no significant difference between satisfaction level of different educational groups towards motor insurance policies

Table 7

Satisfaction level of different educational groups towards motor insurance policies

Variables		Sum of Squar es	df	Mean Squar e	F	Sig.
Quality Product	Between	59.84	3	19.94	2.22	.079
	Groups	0		7	8	
	Within Groups	214.4	196	1.094		
	Total	274.3	199			
		80	20			
Psychological Safety	Between	32.14	3	10.71	2.11	.070
	Groups	0		3	7	
	Within Groups	99.44	196	.507		
	Total	131.5	199			
		80				

Insurable Risk	Between	25.00	3	8.334	1.03	.450
	Groups	1			8	
	Within Groups	203.2	196	1.037		
		19				
	Total	228.2	199			
		20				
Agents motivation	Between	50.52	3	16.84	1.43	.310
	Groups	0		0	2	
	Within Groups	169.8	196	.867		
		60				
	Total	220.3	199			
		80				
Financial Securities	Between	9.152	3	3.051	2.59	.015
	Groups				4	
	Within Groups	166.3	196	.849		
		68				
	Total	175.5	199			
		20				
Coverage meets expectations	Between	25.23	3	8.411	11.3	.056
	Groups	2			39	
	Within Groups	145.3	196	.742		
		88				
	Total	170.6	199			
		20				
Individual attention	Between	17.81	3	5.938	9.16	.030
	Groups	5			0	
	Within Groups	127.0	196	.648		
		60				
	Total	144.8	199			
		75				

Flexibility	Between	33.12	3	11.04	12.4	.020
	Groups	1		0	72	
	Within Groups	173.4	196	.885		
		99				
	Total	206.6	199			
		20				
Reasonably priced	Between	22.43	3	7.478	2.68	.055
	Groups	3			5	
	Within Groups	168.7	196	.861		
		62				
	Total	191.1	199			
		95				
Customer relationship management	Between	27.23	3	9.079	1.75	.430
	Groups	6			1	
	Within Groups	165.5	196	.844		
		19				
	Total	192.7	199			
		55				

Source: primary data

The satisfaction level of insurance policy holders is evaluated with the help of ANOVA table. According to the education level of respondents Quality of products (.070), Psychological safety (.070), Insurable risk (.450), Agent's motivation (.310), Coverage meets expectation (.056), Reasonably priced (.055) and Customer relationship are same across the group. Overall anova table shows, there is no significant difference in the satisfaction level of respondents based on their educational qualification. While considering Financial securities (.015), Individual attention (.030), and Flexibility (.020) are shows significant difference across educational qualification.

Objective 2 : To Assess the Relationship between Consumer Buying Behaviour and Satisfaction in Motor Insurance Policy holders

Table 8

Relationship between Consumer Buying Behaviour and Satisfaction in Motor Insurance Policy holders

Variables	Mean	SD	QP	PS	IR	AM	FS	CME	IA	F	RP	CRM
Quality Product (QP)	3.67	.929	1									
Psychological Safety(PS)	3.68	.842	.020	1								
Insurable Risk(IR)	3.72	.907	.118	.126	1							
Agents Motivation(AM)	3.24	1.056	.043	.005	.008	1						
Financial Securities(FS)	3.53	1.066	.001	.028	.012	.007	1					
Coverage Meets Expectation(CME)	3.43	.773	.216	.004	.074	.034	.110	1				
Individual Attention(IA)	3.42	.946	.064	.065	.237	.032	.259	.162	1			
Flexibility(F)	3.57	.887	.222	.012	.023	.043	.072	.021	.176	1		
Reasonably Priced(RP)	3.81	2.638	.025	.024	0.36	.027	.048	.065	.038	.098	1	

(CRM)	3.56	1.106	.035	.125	.265	.084	.302	.452	.432	.024	.156	1
-------	------	-------	------	------	------	------	------	------	------	------	------	---

Source: primary data

Descriptive statistics of ten variables are depicted in(Table no8) It can be observed that mean score of select variables in motor insurance projects more than 3. The measurement scale used in the study is parameterised as Strongly disagree SD (1), Disagree-D (2), Neutral-N (3), Agree-A (4), and Strongly agree-SA (5). In each cell of the correlation matrix, we get Pearson’s correlation coefficient and p-value for two-tailed test of significance (in brackets). From the output, we can see that the p-value for two-tailed test of significance is less than 0.05 among Insurable risks (IR)-Qualitative product (QP), Coverage meets expectation (CME)-Qualitative product (QP), Individual attention (IA)-Insurable risks (IR), Individual attention (IA)-Financial security (FS), Individual attention (IA)-Coverage meets expectation (CME), Flexibility (F) Qualitative product (QP), Flexibility (F)-Coverage meets expectation (CME), Flexibility (F)-Individual attention IA), Customer Relationship Management (CRM)-Insurable risks (IR), Customer Relationship Management (CRM)- Financial security (FS), Customer Relationship Management (CRM)-Coverage meets expectation (CME), and Customer Relationship Management (CRM)-Individual attention (IA). From this we can conclude that p-value is significant at 95 percent confidence level between IR-QP, CME-QP, IA-IR, IA-FS, IA-CME, F-QP, F-CME, F-IA, CRM-IR, CRMFS, CRM-CME, and CRM- IA. All other variables are not significantly correlated with each other.

Table 9

The Influences of Buying Behaviour on Consumer Satisfaction with Durbin Watson Test

Model	R	R square	Adj R square	Standard error of the estimate	Change statistics					Durbin watson
					R square change	F change	Df1	Df2	Sig f change	
1	.486	.184	.163	.678	.183	6.231	4	284	.000	1.823

Source: primary data

In the model summary shown in (Table no 9), R-square shows the “goodness of fit” of the model in percentage. R-square for this model is .184, which means that the independent variables (IVs) can explain about 18.4% of the change in dependent variable (DV). However, the R square value tends to be a bit inflated when the number of IVs is more or when the number of cases is large. The ‘adjusted R square’ gives more accurate information about the fitness of the model. Here, an adjusted R square value of 0.163 would mean that the IVs in the model can predict 16.3 percent of the variance of the DV (an adjusted R square value in the range of 0.10 to 0.20 is acceptable in social science research). As far as the Durbin-Watson value is concerned, it is a guide to detecting autocorrelation, with the ideal value being 2.085 (suggesting no autocorrelation).

Table 10

The Influences of Buying Behaviour on Consumer Satisfaction using ANOVA

Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig
regression	15.897	5	3.284	6.581	.000
residual	78.452	284	.652		
total	94.349	289			

Source: primary data

ANOVA shows that the model can predict DV using IVs. Here, the alpha value is .000, which shows that there is highly significant difference between the group means.

Table 11

The Influences of Buying Behaviour on Consumer Satisfaction

Model	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardied coefficients	t	sig
1	B	Std.	Beta		

Error					
(Constant)	1.251	.282		4.848	.000
Quality product	.028	.054	.035	.512	.561
Psychological safety	.218	.028	.285	4.899	.000
Insurable risks	.049	.054	.039	.785	.645
Agent's motivation	.136	.028	.043	.547	.854
Financial security	.141	.048	.200	3.888	.043

Source : Primary Data

Finally, in Table 11 of the coefficients, the significance level of psychological safety (PS) and financial security (FS) are less than 0.05, so they are significant. However, the significance levels of qualitative product (QP), insurable risks (IR) and agent's motivation (AM) are more than 0.05, so they are insignificant.

Objective: 3 To analyse factors affecting Motor insurance policyholders

Table 12
Factors influencing motor insurance

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.868
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	4170.820
	Df	153
	Sig.	.000

Source : Primary Data

The Kaiser Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett test of sphericity was chosen to measure the degree of samples covered. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin sampling adequacy measure 86.8 per cent show that there is a high sampling adequacy to study the factors to be considered the perception of motor insurance holders. Bartletts Sphericity test is important (approximate Chi-

Square 4170.820; p value is 0.000, less than 5 per cent) suggest a union of component of the different reason for considering factors of motor insurance in Kerala.

Table 13

Communalities of motor insurance policy holders considering the factors for joining motor insurance claim in Kerala

Communalities

Factors	Initial	Extraction
Sense of security	1.000	.740
Future financial losses	1.000	.830
Future losses or damages in future	1.000	.805
Smooth travel in long distance	1.000	.779
Timely settlement	1.000	.860
Commendable settlement procedure	1.000	.790
prompt services to the customers	1.000	.785
personalized customer care service	1.000	.702
Personalized insurance plan	1.000	.833
Protection for my vehicle	1.000	.709
Risk coverage plans create confusion	1.000	.773
Always willing to help customers	1.000	.696
Create confidence among the customers	1.000	.800
maintain transparent service to the customer	1.000	.699
quality services to customers	1.000	.771
maintains error free records	1.000	.794
safe in transaction with motor insurance companies	1.000	.701
Facilities available to the Customer	1.000	.817

Source : Primary Data

From the above Table, extraction communalities value for each variable identified has got moderate and high value. For example, the extracted value for the component quality services to customers got 77.1 per cent of the variance explained by the extracted factors. Facilities available to the Customer got highest extraction value which come to 81.7 per cent. Similarly, almost all variable has high and medium values, where variants are explained. If a particular variable has low communality, it means that the extracted factors are not able to explain such variants in that variable and it may be dropped from the analysis.

Table 14

Total variance explained for motor insurance policy holders considering the factors of choosing the motor insurance policy

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	8.555	47.527	47.527	8.555	47.527	47.527	5.180	28.777	28.777
2	1.959	10.886	58.413	1.959	10.886	58.413	3.699	20.550	49.327
3	1.287	7.150	65.563	1.287	7.150	65.563	1.826	10.144	59.471
4	1.076	5.980	71.543	1.076	5.980	71.543	1.686	9.368	68.838
6	.722	4.009	81.137						
7	.612	3.399	84.535						
8	.455	2.530	87.065						
9	.413	2.295	89.360						
10	.360	1.999	91.360						

11	.290	1.612	92.972						
12	.269	1.496	94.468						
13	.235	1.308	95.776						
14	.218	1.214	96.990						
15	.184	1.022	98.012						
16	.154	.858	98.869						
17	.118	.658	99.527						
18	.085	.473	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

The above Table indicates about the useful factors with eigen values greater than 1. In the above table there are 4 factors identified. The cumulative percentage obtained from extraction sum of squared loading indicate that with the help of 1 extracted factor, it is possible to explain 47.52 per cent of the variance. If the second factor, consider 58.43 per cent variance can be identified. Similarly, while considering 4 factors all together, it is possible to explain 71.54 per cent. This is in fact considered to be one of the most essence of the factor defined. Hence it is concluded that with the help of 4 factors, to be a certain extent the rating of the factors considering motor insurance can be identified.

Table 15

Rotated component matrix of motor insurance policy holders considering the perception

Rotated Component Matrix^a				
	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Sense of security	.884	.1 81	.0 82	.18 8
Future financial losses	.860	.1 60	.1 25	.08 5
Future losses or damages in future	.850	.2 24	.0 56	.06 8

Smooth travel in long distance	.717	.3 99	.1 37	- .13 3
Timely settlement	.188	.6 93	.3 02	.30 5
Commendable settlement procedure	.085	.6 49	.3 00	.09 2
prompt services to the customers	.068	.6 29	.2 72	.07 3
personalized customer care service	- .133	.5 97	.0 91	- .18 7
Personalized insurance plan	.147	- .1 33	.8 51	.14 8
Protection for my vehicle	.265	.3 05	.8 14	.11 2
Risk coverage plans create confusion	.209	.0 92	.7 59	.26 9
Always willing to help customers	.385	.6 68	.1 95	.73 1
Create confidence among the customers	.504	.5 47	- .2 52	.84 5
maintain transparent service to the customer	.160	.1 03	.1 45	.82 5
quality services to customers	.333	.3 81	.1 28	.72 1
maintains error free records	.289	.1 39	.0 47	.80 9

Source : Primary Data

The above Table clearly shows the 4-component extracted from the rotated component matrix. The Table 15 clearly shows the relative correlation between variables (factor loading) varies interchangeably. The Table clearly shows that factor loading value of one, two, three components which are high and it is to be grouped under on the 1st factor. Four, five, six and seven belonging to the 2nd factor. Nine, eleven and twelve is placed at 3rd factor and Eight, thirteen and eighteen are the 4th factors The following table clearly show the details regarding the classification.

Table 16
Four factors influencing motor insurance

Factors	Values
Factor I: Future Security	
Sense of security	.884
Future financial losses	.860
Future losses or damages in future	.850
Smooth travel in long distance	.717
Factor II: Prompt Service	
Timely settlement	.693
Commendable settlement procedure	.649
prompt services to the customers	.629
personalized customer care service	.597
Factor III: Risk Coverage	
Personalized insurance plan	.851
Protection for my vehicle	.814

Risk coverage plans create confusion	.759
Factor IV: Employee Behavior	
Always willing to help customers	.731
Create confidence among the customers	.845
maintain transparent service to the customer	.825
quality services to customers	.721
maintains error free records	.809

Source : Primary Data

Ho There is no significant difference between educational qualification of respondents towards factors affecting motor insurance holders

Table No: 17

Difference between educational qualification of respondents towards factors affecting motor insurance holders

ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Future Security	Between Groups	.762	3	.381	.287	.752
	Within Groups	106.418	287	1.330		
	Total	107.181	290			
Prompt Service	Between Groups	.162	3	.081	.093	.911
	Within Groups	69.501	287	.869		
	Total	69.663	290			
Risk Coverage	Between Groups	.460	3	.230	.355	.702

	Within Groups	51.806	287	.648		
	Total	52.265	290			
Employee Behaviour	Between Groups	1.169	3	.584	.500	.608
	Within Groups	93.506	287	1.169		
	Total	94.675	290			

Source: computed from primary data

From the above table it is clear that there is no significant difference between educational qualification of respondents towards factors affecting motor insurance holders. All the p values are more than 0.05, so the null hypothesis is accepted. From the analysis it is clear that educational qualification has no significant influence on taking motor insurance.

Table No 18

Sources of Awareness

Variables	N	Median	Mean	Chi-square	Sig
Relatives	290	4.500	3.64	7.600	.022
Friends	290	5.200	3.45		
Internet	290	6.800	3.69		
Newspaper	290	4.500	3.64		
Tv/radio advertisement	290	4.500	3.64		
Insurance agent	290	5.200	3.45		

Source: computed from primary data

From the above table it is clear that there is a statistical difference in source of awareness of different motor insurance holders. Internet (median: 6.80) is the major source of awareness regards motor insurance.

Objective 4 : To analyze the challenges faced by the motor vehicle insurance holders

Table No:19

Challenges faced by the motor vehicle insurance holders

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Difficulty in deciding a company due to lot of options	290	3.76	1.143
Assessing the credibility of the insurance company	290	1.61	.922
Too many plans to choose from - Too much unnecessary information creates confusion	290	1.86	.798
Difficulty in finding a plan appropriate to my needs	290	2.53	1.075
Absence of affordable plans	290	4.24	.759
Paper works (time, cost, formalities) for Policy taking procedures	290	3.29	1.393
Paper works (time, cost, formalities) for Policy renewal procedures	290	3.05	1.258
Time taken for Policy settlement procedures	290	3.22	1.406

Source: computed from primary data

Absence of affordable plans (4.24) is the most prominent challenge faced by the respondents. Difficulty in deciding a company due to lot of options (3.76) was the another challenge. But the respondents have positive attitude towards Assessing the credibility of the insurance company(1.61).

H₀: There is no significant difference in challenges faced by motor insurance holders based on their gender

Table No 20**Challenges faced by motor insurance holders based on their gender**

Test variables	Leven's test for equality of variance		T test for equality of means		
	F	Sig	t	df	Sig
Difficulty in deciding a company due to lot of options	0.031	.785	2.025	289	.038
Assessing the credibility of the insurance company	2.308	.158	2.095	289	.047
Too many plans to choose from - Too much unnecessary information creates confusion	5.162	.025	4.046	289	.000
Difficulty in finding a plan appropriate to my needs	7.425	.008	3.275	289	.004
Absence of affordable plans	5.984	.014	0.310	289	.657
Paper works (time, cost, formalities) for Policy taking procedures	5.258	.018	3.772	289	.002
Paper works (time, cost, formalities) for Policy renewal procedures	0.185	.068	2.180	289	.031
Time taken for Policy settlement procedures	4.358	.038	0.770	289	.442

Source: computed from primary data

A greater than 0.05 significance of F statistics f reject Levene's null hypothesis that variances are not equal. In all such cases the t statistics of independent samples t test, most of the values are below 0.05. which means there is a significant difference in challenges faced by motor insurance holders based on their gender. But while considering "absence of affordable plans" shows the challenges faced by both male and female were same with a p value of 0.657.

It can be concluded that the motor insurance holders were facing lot of challenges, but while considering the gender it is different from each other.

H₀ There is no significant difference in challenges faced by motor insurance holders based on their education qualification.

Table No: 21

Challenges faced by motor insurance holders based on their education qualification.

Variables		Sum of		Mean	F	Sig.
		Squares	df	Square		
Difficulty in deciding a company due to lot of options	Between Groups	59.840	3	19.947	0.815	.069
	Within Groups	214.480	287	1.094		
	Total	274.320	290			
Assessing the credibility of the insurance company	Between Groups	32.140	3	10.713	0.269	.070
	Within Groups	99.440	287	.507		
	Total	131.580	290			
Too many plans to choose from - Too much unnecessary information creates confusion	Between Groups	25.001	3	8.334	0.038	.550
	Within Groups	203.219	287	1.037		
	Total	228.220	290			
Difficulty in finding a plan appropriate to my needs	Between Groups	50.520	3	16.840	2.432	.010
	Within Groups	169.860	287	.867		
	Total	220.380	290			
Absence of affordable plans	Between Groups	9.152	3	3.051	2.544	.015
	Within Groups	166.368	287	.849		
	Total	175.520	290			
Paper works (time, cost, formalities) for Policy taking procedures	Between Groups	25.232	3	8.411	11.339	.056
	Within Groups	145.388	287	.742		
	Total	170.620	290			
Paper works (time, cost, formalities) for Policy renewal procedures	Between Groups	17.815	3	5.938	4.160	.000
	Within Groups	127.060	287	.648		
	Total	144.875	290			
Time taken for Policy	Between Groups	33.121	3	11.040	1.22	.548

settlement procedures	Within Groups	173.499	287	.885
	Total	206.620	290	

Source: computed from primary data

From the above table it is clear that there is no significant difference between educational qualification of respondents towards factors affecting motor insurance holders. Most the p values are more than 0.05, so the null hypothesis is accepted. From the analysis it is clear that educational qualification has no significant influence on challenges faced by the motor insurance policy holders. But in the case of Difficulty in finding a plan appropriate to my needs (.010) and Absence of affordable plans (.015) showed a significant difference in terms of the qualification of the respondents.

Objective 5: To analyze the reason for choosing motor insurance policy

Table No:22
Reason for choosing motor insurance policy

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
As a means of Tax savings	290	3.76	.143
As part of life Discipline	290	2.61	.982
As a means to Safety	290	2.86	.798
Due to RTO rules	290	2.53	1.055
As an Investment to protect my asset	290	4.24	.709
Cashless settlement at the time of damage	290	1.29	1.393
Influence of family and relatives	290	3.05	1.258
Fear due to past experience of friends and relatives	290	3.22	1.406

Source: computed form primary data

Most of the respondents take motor insurance for protecting their asset with a mean score of 4.24. Also the respondents were treat as a means of tax (3.76) savings and fear due to past experiences

(3.22). but the respondents are less influenced by cashless settlement at the time of damage with a mean score of 1.29.

H₀ There is no significant difference between reasons for choosing motor insurance policy based on gender wise

Table No:23
Reasons for choosing motor insurance policy based on gender wise

Test variables	Leven's test for equality of variance		T test for equality of means		
	F	Sig	t	df	Sig
As a means of Tax savings	2.431	.035	2.125	289	.028
As part of life Discipline	2.308	.048	2.195	289	.037
As a means to Safety	5.162	.025	4.046	289	.001
Due to RTO rules	7.425	.008	3.275	289	.003
As an Investment to protect my asset	5.984	.014	0.310	289	.657
Cashless settlement at the time of damage	5.258	.018	3.772	289	.002
Influence of family and relatives	0.185	.068	2.180	289	.031
Fear due to past experience of friends and relatives	4.358	.038	0.770	289	.442

Source: computed form primary data

While considering the independent sample t test it is clear that the hypothesis has been rejected. Which means most of the p values are less than 0.05.so there is a significant difference between reason for choosing motor insurance policy based on gender wise. But in the case of protection of their assets, p value is more than 0.05 and it means that there is a difference between male and female towards reasons for choosing motor insurance policy.

CHAPTER IV

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Insurance is one of the key industries in the service sector of every country. In a service industry like insurance, the quality of customer services holds primary significance, particularly in context of sustained business growth. The Indian general insurance sector has started showing signs of significant changes after the opening of the industry to private players. In today's hyper competitive environment, insurers are operating under shrinking premiums, growing customer expectations and tightening regulations which are narrowing their margins. With the entry of private players, the competition is becoming intense. Innovative products, smart marketing and aggressive distribution have enabled private general insurers to capture considerable percentage of market share and established their strong presence in the market.

Customer retention is an important perspective that has to be taken into consideration more seriously by Motor Insurance Companies. In a service industry like insurance, the quality of the customer service acquires crucial significance in the context of sustained business growth. However no serious study has been conducted to evaluate **consumers'** decision making in motor insurance policies. So the proposed study is conducted to evaluate the same.

4.1 Objectives of the study

- To analyze the satisfaction level of different motor insurance policyholders.
- To Assess the Relationship between Consumer Buying Behaviour and Satisfaction in Motor Insurance Policyholders.
- To analyze factors affecting Motor insurance policyholders.
- To analyze the challenges faced by the motor vehicle insurance holders.
- To analyze the reason for choosing motor insurance policy.

4.2. Summary of Major Findings

- Psychological Safety (PS) was found to be the most prominent attribute among female respondents.
- Customer relationship management is the least prominent among female customers
- There is significant difference in the satisfaction level of motor insurance holders across categories of gender in the cases of insurable risk, individual attention and reasonably priced.
- There is significant difference in the satisfaction level of motor insurance holders across categories of educational qualification in the cases of financial securities, Individual attention and Flexibility.
- While assessing the relationship between Consumer Buying Behavior and Satisfaction in Motor Insurance Policyholders, it was found that there is a significant correlation between Insurable risks (IR)-Qualitative product (QP), Coverage meets expectation (CME)-Qualitative product (QP), Individual attention (IA)-Insurable risks (IR), Individual attention (IA)-Financial security (FS), Individual attention (IA)-Coverage meets expectation (CME), Flexibility (F)- Qualitative product (QP), Flexibility (F)-Coverage meets expectation (CME), Flexibility (F)-Individual attention IA), Customer Relationship Management (CRM)-Insurable risks (IR), Customer Relationship Management (CRM)- Financial security (FS), Customer Relationship Management (CRM)-Coverage meets expectation (CME), and Customer Relationship Management (CRM)-Individual attention (IA).
- While measuring the influences of Buying Behaviour on Consumer Satisfaction, it was found that there is a significant influence of psychological safety (PS) and financial security (FS) on consumer satisfaction.
- Internet was found to be the major source of awareness regarding motor insurance policy
- The four factors that influence the motor insurance policy holders while considering a motor in policy are Future Security, Prompt Service, Risk coverage and Employee Behaviour.
- It was found that educational qualification has no significant influence on the consumer while considering to purchase a motor insurance.

- While analyzing the challenges faced by motor insurance policy holders, it was found that Absence of affordable plans is the most prominent challenge faced by the respondents. Difficulty in deciding a company due to lot of options was the second prominent challenge. But the respondents depicted a positive attitude towards Assessing the credibility of the insurance company.
- There is a significant difference in challenges faced by motor insurance holders based on their gender.
- There is a significant difference in challenges faced by motor insurance holders based on their educational qualification in case of Difficulty in finding a plan appropriate to my needs and Absence of affordable plans.
- There is a significant difference in reason for choosing motor insurance policy based on the gender of the respondents.

SUGGESTIONS

- There is significant difference in the satisfaction level of motor insurance holders across categories of gender and educational qualification. The policy providers must take utmost care in understanding the reason for this and also take necessary steps to ensure high level of customer satisfaction
- It was found that psychological safety (PS) and financial security (FS) had a higher influence on the buying behaviour of the policy holders. Hence the policy providers should focus on providing a sense of safety as well as financial security to the policyholders
- Internet was found to be the major source of awareness regarding the motor insurance policy. Hence this medium should be utilized well enough to get the most out of it and also focus should be given on other medias to make the public aware of such policies.
- Respondents found it hard to identify plans affordable to them. Hence the policy providers should take care of designing customized policies affordable to the customers belonging to all categories of the society.

CONCLUSION

Even though the growth rate of the insurance industry is far beyond the international growth rates and standards, the annual reports of the General insurance companies reveals that the Indian insurance industry is growing year after year. After the introduction of private companies in the General insurance sector, the companies are facing tight competition between themselves. This stringent competition forces them to go for innovative strategies and diversified products and services. The healthy competitions between the general insurance companies are good for the customers in the sense that it will give them better choices and alternatives. While struggling to exist and retain in the market, the companies forget to think about the customer. The findings of the current study points out that both the public sector and private sector companies are not discharging their obligation to their customers in the proper manner. No company can exist in the market without customer satisfaction and retention. To attain customer satisfaction, the companies should ensure that they are providing their best to the customers in all its aspect.

Bibliography

Books

1. Banerjee, B.N., Globalization: Liberalizing the Indian Insurance Sector, Response Books, New Delhi, 2000.
2. Bateson, J.E.G; and Hoffman D.K., Managing Services Marketing; Text and Readings, The Dryden Press, New York, 1999.
3. Berry, Leonard L.; A. Parasuraman., Marketing Services: Competing Through Quality. New York: Free Press, 1991.
4. Besterfield, D.H., Quality Control, Prentice Hall, New Jersey, 1994.
5. Bluestein, Abram; Michael Moriarty; Ronald J Sanderson, The Customer Satisfaction Audit. Axminster: Cambridge Strategy Publications, 2003.
6. Brown, R.C., Health Industry, Edward Arnold Publishers Ltd., London, 1961.
7. Burtchett, F.F., Investments and Investment Policy, Longmans, Green & Co., New York, 1939.
8. Gerhard Raab, RiadA.Ajami, VidyaranyaB.Gargeya, G. Jason Goddard., customer Relationship Management, Ashgate Publishing Group, Farnham, 2008.
9. Gerson, Richard F., Measuring Customer Satisfaction: A Guide to Managing Quality Services, Course Technology Publications, Menlo Park, CA, USA, 1993.
10. Gronroos C., Strategic Management and Marketing in Service Sector, Marketing Science Institute, Cambridge, 1982.
11. Gungor, Husejin, Emotional Satisfaction of Customer Contacts, Amsterdam University Press, Amsterdam, 2007.

12. Jani, B.M., Impact of Financial Liberalization Policy in India, Himalaya Publishing House, New Delhi, 1997.
13. Khan, M.A., Theory and Practice of Insurance, Educational Book House, Aligarh, 2001.
14. Ron S. Kenett, Silva Salini., Statistics in Practice-Modern Analysis of Customer Surveys with Application using R, Wiley Publishing House, USA,2011.
15. Rosander A.C., “Application of quality control in service industry”, ASQC quality press, 1985.
16. Rust, R. T., and R. C. Oliver., Service quality: Insights and managerial implications from the frontier. In Service Quality: New Directions in Theory and Practice, (Ed), Rust, R. T., and R. C. Oliver. London: Sage Publications, 1994.
17. Rust, R.T., Zeithmal, V.A. and Lemon, K.N., Driving Customer Equity: How customer lifetime value is reshaping corporate strategy, Free Press, Boston, 2000.
18. Shrivastava, D.C. and Shrivastava, S., Indian Insurance Industry: Transition and Prospects, New Century Publications, New Century Publications, New Delhi, 2001.
19. Zeithamal V.A and Mary Jo Bitner, “Service Marketing “,Third Edition, TataMCGraw Hill Publishing company Ltd, New Delhi, 2003.
20. Zeithaml, V.A., Parasuraman A. and Berry, L.L., Delivering Service Quality, Free Press, New York, NY, 1990.

Working Papers and Journals

21. Ajay K Rajan&MukeshDhunna “Liberalization of insurance sector: social implication” Indian Management studies Vol.6, No.1, 2002, pp. 106-117.
22. AlopeTewary “Insurance - The latest Buzzword in the Indian Economy” Banking Finance Jan 2003 pp. 10-12.
23. AlokGoel and SeemaReum, “Service Quality Measurement and Customer Satisfaction in Indian BPO Industry”, International Business, 2010, Vol. 6, Issue 6, p. 33.
24. Armstrong, Ed and Buse, P. (1996). “You’ve got the green light, what’s it worth?” ABA Banking Journal, Vol. 88, Sept., 13-18.
25. Ashok Kumar. M, Rajesh. R, “Whether Today’s Customers are satisfied? - A Study with Banks”; Indian journal of Marketing, pg. 56-60, September, 2009.
26. Atmanand (2003), “Insurance and Disaster Management in the Indian context “, Disaster prevention and management, 12(4), General review, [<http://www.Emeraldinsight.com>
27. Boulding, William; Karla, Ajay; Staelin, R; Zeithaml, V.A, A Dynamic Model of Service Quality; From Expectations to Behavioral intentions, Journal of Marketing Research, 1993, Vol. 30, pp. 7-27.
28. Bhave, A. (2002), “Customer Satisfaction Measurement”, Quality and Productivity Journal, pp. 25-30.
29. Bhat Y. S. (1991), ‘Customer Service’, Yogakshema, Vol35: No: 7, pg. 11-12.
30. Bitner, M.J. (1992), “Services capes: the impact of physical surroundings on customers and employees”, Journal of Marketing, Vol. 56, pp. 57-71.
31. Cardozo.R.N ;(1965), “An Experimental study of customer effort, expectations and satisfaction”, Journal of Marketing Research, vol.2 (August), pg. 244-52.

32. Churchill Jr, Gilbert A; Carol Suprenant, An Investigation into the Determinants or Customer satisfaction, *Journal of Marketing Research*, November 1982, Vol. 19, No. 4, Special Issue on Causal Modeling, pp. 491-504
33. Don O' Sullivan. (2009), "Does customer satisfaction influence the relationship between earnings and firm value?" *Marketing Letter*, Vol. 20, No.4, pp.337-351.
34. Dr. Abdel Moniem Ahmed, Bradford University, & Prof. Mohamed Zairi, Bradford University School of Management, "Customer Satisfaction: The Driving Force for Winning Business Excellence Award" Bradford University, Working Paper No .02/06.(March 2002).
35. Dr. DaleepPandita Customer Service in Changing Market Scenario, *The Insurance Institute of Journal*, January -June 2003, Pg.38.
36. Eugene W. Anderson, ClaesFornell and Roland T. Rust (1997), "Customer satisfaction, Productivity, and Profitability: Difference between Goods and Services". *Marketing Science*. Vol.16, No. 2, pp. 129-145.
37. Gorski, Lorraine (2002a). "The New Producers." *Best's Review*, May 2002, p.45-48.
38. Gorski, Lorraine (2002b). "Banking on Policy Holders". *Best's Review*, July 2002, p.44.
39. Gregory A. Kuhlemeyer& Garth H. Allen, "Consumer Satisfaction with Life Insurance: A Benchmarking Survey", *The journal of Association for Financial counseling and Planning Education*, Vol.10 (1), 1999.
40. Goodman J.A., Malech, A. R ,Bargatze, G.F. and Ledbetter, C. (1988) " Converting a Desire for Quality Service in to Actions with Measurable Impact" *Journal of Retail Banking* Vol.10, no.4,pp 10-22.
41. Goodwin C. and Ross I. (1989), "Salient Dimensions Of Perceived Fairness in Resolution of Service Complaints", *Journal of Satisfaction, Dissatisfaction and Complaining Behavior*, 2: 87-92.
42. Handbook on Indian Insurance Statistics 2009-10.

43. IRDA Annual Reports.
44. Jagendra Kumar, "This Fiscal may be deuce, for Private and Public Sector General Insurers", *The Insurance Times*, Vol. XXX No. 6, June, 2010.
45. Johnston, R. and Silvestro, R. (1990), "The determinants of service quality – a customer-based approach", in *The Proceedings of the Decision Science Institute Conference*, San Diego, CA, November.
46. Lehtinen, J.R. and Lehtinen, U. (1982), "Service quality: a study of quality dimensions", unpublished Working Paper, Service Management Institute, Helsinki.
47. Muller W. (1991) "Gaining Competitive Advantage through Customer Satisfaction)", *European Management Journal*, June.pp.201-221
48. Olahavshy.R.W and J.A.Miller, 1972," consumer expectations, product performance and perceived product quality", *Journal of Marketing Research*, vol 9 (February) pg. 19-21.
49. Olson.J.C and D.Dover, 1979,'Disconfirmation of Consumer Expectations through Product Trial', *Journal of Applied Psychology*, vol.46 (April) pg. 375-384.
50. Rana, J.K., "The Ticket size of General Insurance Market in India". *The Insurance Times*, Vol. XXXII No.08, August, 2012.
51. Swartz, T.A. and Brown, S.W. (1989), "Consumer and provider expectations and experiences evaluating professional service quality", *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, Vol. 17 No. 2, pp. 189-95.
52. Teans. R Kenneth (1993), "Expectations, Performance Evaluation, and Customer Perception of Quality". *Journal of Marketing*, 57 (October), pg. 18-34.
53. VinayVerma. 'How to improve customer service in General Insurance Industry?' *The Insurance Times*: Vol: XX11 No: 7 July 2002, pg. 31-32
54. AlopeTewary "Insurance - The latest Buzzword in the Indian Economy" *Banking Finance* Jan 2003 pp. 10-12.

55. Armstrong, Ed and Buse, P. (1996). "You've got the green light, what's it worth?" *ABA Banking Journal*, Vol. 88, Sept., 13-18.

56. Atmanand (2003), "Insurance and Disaster Management in the Indian context ", *Disaster prevention and management*, 12(4), General review, [<http://www.Emeraldinsight.com>

Websites

<http://www.irda.org>

<http://www.gicindia.com>

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE BUYING BEHAVIOR OF MOTORINSURANCE POLICYHOLDERS- A STUDY OF KOTTARAKARAMUNICIPALITY

Dr. Sumi Alex

*Assistant Professor, Research and P.G Department of Commerce,
St. Gregorios College, Kottarakara, Kerala*

Dr. P.S Aithal

Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka

ABSTRACT

Purpose: India is one of the largest automotive sectors, in the world in terms of vehicle production, in the financial year 2021, the total production volume of vehicles in India was around 22.7 million units. A drop in the sales volume of vehicles was witnessed in the past years. COVID-19 has impacted negatively on India Motor Insurance Industry because of the lockdown put across the country for a long period leading to a halt in businesses. New automobile purchases constitute a major portion of the premiums, and hence the lockdown and virtual stoppage of business may aggravate the situation. Lack of purchase of new vehicles is one of the biggest challenges faced by the industry. Normally, that would be compensated for by increasing the coverage net of existing vehicles, a vast majority of which fall out of the insurance net by the third and fourth years. The present study focus to identifies the various factors which influence the consumers in the Kottarakara Municipality, Kerala to select an Insurance company.

Methodology: In 2021, Motor insurance Industry in Kerala accounted for 34.1% of the non-life insurance premiums earned, followed by health insurance at 29.5%, Demographic variables play a very important role in understanding customers' perceptions. Thus the impact of demographic profiles was also assessed. A survey of 120 respondents was taken and analyzed to understand the factors that influence the insurance company's selection decisions.

Findings/ Result: The study findings revealed that according to the ranks given the most important factors that influence customers are proximity, company services, infrastructure, convenience, security, technology, responsiveness, reputation, image, and ownership.

Paper type: Analytical Research Paper

Keywords: motor insurance, policy holders, customer perception

1. INTRODUCTION

The Indian Motor Insurance Market is one of the most widely demanded Motor Insurance Market as the people are keen to get secure and have a protective shield occurred because of a collision or other mishappening. The development of the economy depends on the soundness of the financial system. The insurance sector is one of the major players in the financial system. In the FY21 Post-Covid, rising demand for personal mobility space is leading to a shift in vehicle ownership patterns and may create an opportunity for motor insurers. The India Motor Insurance Market is growing at a CAGR of >3% over the next 5 yrs. A high level of competition is the most important factor in influencing the structure and activities of the insurance system around the globe. More and more insurance facilities are made available in every part of the country even in small cities, towns, and rural areas. The growing awareness among the people about the need and the increase in the number of road accidents paved the way to the scope and expansion of this sector at a large. Hence there is a wide scope of choices in front of the customers they don't want to comprise anything. This leads to creating a high pressure among the Insurance companies which in turn results in a better and standard quality of service. Any sort of dissatisfaction among the customers will force them to switch from the poor to a much better one. To prevent the migration of customers and attract new ones, the insurance companies need to understand the preferences of the customers to offer the services required by them. With intensified competition in the industry, the insurance companies need to understand "How do customers choose their insurance company? Exploring and evaluating such information will help companies to identify the appropriate marketing strategies that are needed to survive in the market.

This study is an attempt towards finding out what factors most influence customers while making company selections. The variations in the perception of choices about factors will provide a useful insight to insurance companies when selecting their marketing strategies.

2. LITERATUREREVIEW

Mathur D and Tripathi A (2014) investigated Factors affecting Customers' choice for the selection of Insurance Companies in Ajmer city India. The study revealed that the Proximity of the company, Infrastructure, and services renders by the company, convenience in terms of security and privacy, Technological activities, Image of the company, reputation, prompt response, and ownership were the essential factors influencing the customer's choice of insurance companies. It also found out that customers are influenced by the guidance of the members of the staff.

Shuthi, P. et al (2014) investigated factors affecting the demand for insurance in Davangere City. It found that legal factor is the main stimulating factor for the purchase of insurance and motor insurance and health insurance for migrants are found to be driven the insurance market as a compulsory business, while the attitude of non-insurance users was the basic demotivating factor influencing the non-users remain as they are.

S Krishnamurthy, S V Mony, Nani Jhaveri, Sandeep Bakhshi, Ramesh Bhat, and M R Dixit (2005), in the paper titled, "Insurance Industry in I explained the status and growth of Indian Insurance Industry after liberalization and also presents future India: Structure, Performance, and Future Challenges", clearly challenges and opportunities linked with the Insurance. The paper

has drawn attention to the emerging structure, and role of bancassurance, agents, and customer services in the success of the life insurance business.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The researcher has gone through primary data i.e. interviewing customers and using schedules. A total of 120 respondents were contacted, the respondents were the customers of insurance companies in the municipality of Kottarakara.

- To identify various factors influencing customers' choice of the insurance company.
- To study the impact of gender and education level on factors influencing customers' choice of the insurance company.

4. RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design used for the purpose was descriptive and various factors are taken into account for understanding the customer's choice of an insurance company.

5. SAMPLE AND DATA COLLECTION

The present study was conducted in the Kottarakara Municipality of Kerala State. A purposive sample of 120 individuals who had an experience with offline and online insurance systems was taken. The respondents were requested to give their responses concerning the factors they would consider while choosing an insurance company.

6. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. Although different factors influencing the customer's choice were taken, it may be needed that other aspects and factors not taken into account needed to be explored and studied.
2. The accuracy of the data purely depends on the responses made by the clients.

7. HYPOTHESIS

Ho- there is no impact of education level and gender on the mean of factors influencing the choice of the insurance company.

Hi- There is an impact of education level and gender on the mean of factors influencing the choice of the insurance company.

8. DATA ANALYSIS

Table 1.1 Demographic profile of Respondents-it contains information regarding age, gender, education level, Income

Details		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	85	70.84
	Female	35	29.16
	Total	120	100
Age	18-25	61	50.83
	26-35	22	18.38

	36-45	18	15
	Above 45	19	15.84
	Total	120	100
Monthlyincome	Below20000	43	35.89
	20000-35000	32	26.66
	35000-50000	30	25
	Above 50000	15	12.5
	Total	120	100
Educationalqualification	Belowhighschool	3	4.17
	Highschool	11	9.16
	Graduate	26	21.67
	Post-graduate	70	65
	Total	120	100

Source:primarydata

MostoftherespondentsareMale(70.84%),Agegroup(50.83%),PostGraduate(65%),andIncomebelow 20000(35.89%).

Table1.2 ModeofoperationofInsurance Policies

Modeofoperation	Percentage
Internetbanking	17
Mobilebanking	7
Debitcard	22
Physicallyvisitingcompany	54

Mostofthecustomersoperatetheirinsurancepoliciesbyphysicallyvisitingthecompanyandtheleastam ountofcustomersresorttomobilebanking.

Table1.3T-testresultforGenderandEducationlevel

Factors	Gender	Educationlevel
Proximity	.21854	.00032
Company services andinfrastructure	.00046	.06889
Convenience	.26774	.00002
Security	.75731	.27451
Technology	.94782	.00005
Responsiveness	.49108	.70191
Reputation	.96601	.62516
Image	.34758	0
Ownership	.37089	.00002

The degree of freedom is greater than 30, hence at 5% two-tailed Table value will be 1.96. For all the factors thecalculated value is less than the tabulated value, so the H0 is accepted. hence there is no impact of education levelandgenderonthemeanoffactorsinfluencingthechoiceoftheinsurancecompany.

9. CONCLUSION

The primary objective of this research was to determine the factors affecting customers' choice of the company selection. The 9 key factors which influence the customers in selecting the insurance companies are proximity, company services, infrastructure, convenience, security, technology, responsiveness, reputation, image, and ownership. The values of variances have been derived which entails that the first factor is more important than the second, factor 2 is more important than the third, and so on. Thus the companies should focus more on factors like locations and branch networks which the customers perceive as the most important factors. As per the study, there is no significant impact of gender and education on factors influencing customers' choice of the company. Thus the company does not have to emphasize the segmentation of the market based on demographics to understand the customer's preferences and choice of factors. Better services will surely put the customer on the right path.

10. REFERENCE

1. Arrow, K. J. (1965). „Insurance, Risk and Resource Allocation“ in “Foundations of Insurance Economics”, G. Dionne and S. E. Harrington (eds.), Kluwer Academic Publishers.
2. Beck, T. and I. Webb (2003) “Economic, Demographic, and Institutional Determinants of Life Insurance Consumption Across Countries”, *World Bank Economic Review*, Vol. 17; pp 51-88.
3. Kumar, N., Cohen, M. A., Bishop, C. E., & Wallack, S. S. (1995). Understanding the factors behind the decision to purchase varying coverage amounts of long-term care insurance.
4. Gatnar, E., Walesiak M., 2004. Methods of multidimensional statistical analysis in marketing research, Wroclaw: The Publishing House of Wroclaw University of Economics
5. Dutta M. M. and Mitra G, (2015) Factor affecting Auto Insurance in India. *Indian Journal of Management Science (IJMS)*, 2 December 2015.
6. Ariff U T and Sirajuddin, (2016) A study on Policy holders' Perception towards Motor Vehicle Insurance with special reference to Pollachi Taluk. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education (IJMRME)*, 11(22)

